

IMPACT OF THE INTERNET ON SOCIAL LIFE OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS IN CHENNAI DISTRICT

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Abstract

The student's development and their education system have a fast-changing face in the global level. Due to the internet access the expectation of the parents, corporate and government from the students are high. The main objective of this research study is to explore & investigate student development towards their social life. This study was undertaken using survey method through distribution of a structured questionnaire and data was collected from 327 respondents. The resulting data out of it was processed to data analysis using SPSS software. Results were interpreted using descriptive analysis, t-test, one-way ANOVA. The results shows that there is a significant difference between students' development and personal profile of the students under different factors.

Keywords: Internet Access, Students Behaviour Development, SPSS.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the act of learning things around us. It guides us to easily comprehend and deal with any situation and stabilise us throughout the entire life in every aspect. Education is the first and primary requirement of every human being. Without education we are deficient and our lives are fruitless. Education benefits us to set an objective and helps to progress by working on that throughout the life.

Education is a persistent activity guiding us to accomplish certain objectives, such as imparting knowledge or nurturing skills and personality. Every child must obtain education in his/her relevant age as everyone equal rights for the education from birth.

Technology in Education

Technology that is made use of in the classroom is very beneficial in supporting the students, to follow and ingest what they are being taught.

Today, technology has been integrated into a large number of modules even those that do not correlate to the technology and computer classes. Students make use of technology to come up with their demonstration and also make use of the internet to perform their research on a different topic for their demonstration. In addition, they are using the internet platform for various personal uses and developments.

OBJECTIVES OF THE PRESENT STUDY

- To examine the significant differences among development factors with personal profiles of students.
- To find out the Impact of student's development factors.
- To study the influence of personal profiles of students on total development factors.

METHODOLOGY

The present study is exploratory and analytical in nature and adopted survey method for its findings. This study depends mainly on the primary data collected through the well-structured questionnaire among the respondents. During the period of study, all relevant published information was collected; formal and informal discussions were conducted with the students. The study was conducted in Chennai from different schools. A total of 338 questionnaires were received, on scrutiny of these questionnaires led to rejection of 11 questionnaires on account of incomplete responses and extreme values which were not suitable for the study. The remaining 327 questionnaires were taken for the study. Questionnaires were distributed through google link to different school with the permission of the coordinators. This helped me to collect the data from the required sources.

STATISTICAL TOOLS

Various statistical tools have been appropriately used to analyse the data of different variables according to the nature of the data and objectives of the study using SPSS 21.0. They have been listed out as follows:

1. **Descriptive statistics** has been applied to study various personal profiles such as gender, type of school, class, parent's occupation, parent's education.
2. **"t" test** has been appropriately used to examine the significance of difference between the personal profile & development factors of students.
3. **"F" test** has been appropriately used to examine the significance of difference between the personal profile & development factors of students.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Firstly, this study has majorly focused on higher secondary students in school. Secondly, this study was limited in the context of internet usage of students in their social life. Finally, the study was conducted only in Chennai city.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ivighrehweta & Igere (2014) study stated that most of the students have internet access and they are expert in handling the internet. This study found that majority of students use the internet for their studies, seeking study materials, equip themselves for examination and boost

research work.

Jackson, Eye & Biocca (2003)² found two types of social outcomes are identified in their study. Firstly, students use the internet for fortitude the conversation with those people who are substantially be present in distance. On the other hand, this cybernetic communication somehow decreases face-to-face relationship with family and friends.

Saha, S. R., & Guha, A. K. (2019)³ noticed that the internet has been raised extremely as a platform of communication among the young generation. Most of the children's have retention of the internet through gadgets. However, heavy use of the internet leads to devastation of time and misery among students. This study concluded that use of the internet and social media lead to healthy life and enrich learning practice.

Talooki, Ataee, Gorji, Aghae (2017)⁴ demonstrate that 'use of the internet may effect on students 'behavioural pattern'. By using this electronic gadget, students cannot interconnect with other, but use of massive internet has badly affected students' life. Waste of time, depression and isolation, unemployment, misplacing social bonding etc.

Osunade (2003)⁵ study exposed an important difference between the results of students with Internet access and those without Internet access and there were more male participants than female participants. The male participants prefer night browsing, while the female participants prefer the daytime. Electronic mail (email) is the most popular use of the Internet among students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 illustrates the demographic profiles of respondents according to variables - gender, Type of School, Class of students, Education qualification of parents and occupation.

Table: 1

Factors	Variables	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	123	37.6
	Female	204	62.4
Type Of School	Government School	159	48.6
	Private School	168	51.4
Class of Students	Grade XI	75	22.9
	Grade XII	252	77.1
Education qualification of parents	Illiteracy	15	4.6
	School education	126	38.5
	Higher education	186	56.9
Occupation	Government employee	42	12.8
	Private employee	156	47.7
	Business	75	22.9
	Coolie	-	-
	Others	54	16.5

Table -1 reveals that majority of the respondents are female (62.4%), belonging to the private

school (51.4%), being parent's education with higher education (56.9%) are private employee (47.7%).

Descriptive Statistics of Development Factors

Table: 2

Particulars	Mean	Standard Deviation
Internet access helped meto develop my personal ability	3.97	0.724
Internet access developedmy academic & personal performance	3.45	0.894
By using internet – I am able to overcome negativethoughts	3.83	1.072
Internet helps to developmy positive attitudes	3.99	1.075
I can develop my personality through usageof internet platform	4.29	0.954
I am able to develop mycommunication through usage of internet platform	3.69	0.817
Feeling relief by developing emotional thinking through internet platform	3.73	1.066
Able to enhance mymental strength	4.01	1.021
Able to develop my efficiency	3.79	0.785
Able to maintain my values in the society	3.61	0.979
Able to maintain my culturein the society	4.07	1.006
It helps to develop myconfidence level	3.91	0.897
Able to develop adaptiveness in allsituations.	4.11	1.020
Able to maintain myentertainment up to required level	3.94	1.097
It helps to enhance myintellectual capacity	3.21	0.861
Helps to develop myphysical health	3.53	1.111
Helps to develop mymental health	3.31	1.099
Able to develop mysympathy level.	3.75	1.173
Able to boost my cognition	3.94	1.003
Able to reduce stress	3.97	1.062

Table 2 indicates that personality is the most developed factor for the students followed by adaptiveness to situation, culture learning, mental strength, positive attitude, personal ability, entertainment, reduce stress, confidence level, negative thoughts, efficiency, sympathy level, emotional thinking, communication, values in society, physical health, academic & personal performance, mental health and intellectual capacity.

Significance of Difference in Development Factors between Profile Groups

‘t’ test and ‘F’ test have been conducted to examine the significant difference in **Development Factor (DF)** between or among profile groups and the results are shown in table 2.1 to 2.5

Table 2.1: ‘t’ test has been applied to find out significant difference between gender and development factors

Variables	Mean		Standard Deviation		T value	P Value	Inference
	Male	Female	Male	Female			
Internet access helped me to develop my personal ability	4.27	4.10	.702	.732	0.315	0.575	Not Significant
Internet access developed my academic & personal performance	3.93	4.00	.870	.910	1.129	0.289	Not Significant
By using internet – I am able to overcome negative thoughts	3.63	3.34	1.189	0.982	5.929	0.015	Significant
Internet helps to develop my positive attitudes	3.90	3.78	1.169	1.015	0.531	0.467	Not Significant
I can develop my personality through usage of internet platform	4.10	3.93	0.962	0.947	0.155	0.694	Not Significant
I am able to develop my communication through usage of internet platform	4.32	4.28	0.605	0.923	15.414	0.000	Significant
Feeling relief by developing emotional thinking through internet platform	3.80	3.62	1.114	1.032	0.292	0.589	Not Significant
Able to enhance my mental strength	3.66	3.78	1.007	1.029	2.513	0.114	Not Significant
Able to develop my efficiency	4.12	3.94	0.672	0.840	2.925	0.088	Not Significant
Able to maintain my values in the society	3.95	3.69	1.108	0.881	1.333	0.249	Not Significant
Able to maintain my culture in the society	3.83	3.47	0.912	1.038	5.144	0.024	Significant
It helps to develop my confidence level	3.98	4.13	0.954	0.858	0.075	0.785	Not Significant
Able to develop adaptiveness in all situations.	3.78	3.99	1.004	1.024	0.160	0.689	Not Significant
Able to maintain my entertainment up to required level	4.10	4.12	1.104	1.094	0.208	0.649	Not Significant
It helps to enhance my intellectual capacity	3.78	4.03	0.980	0.768	6.221	0.013	Significant
Helps to develop my physical health	3.15	3.25	1.121	1.106	0.032	0.859	Not Significant
Helps to develop my mental health	3.41	3.60	1.214	1.019	5.136	0.024	Significant
Able to develop my sympathy level.	3.29	3.32	1.136	1.197	0.818	0.366	Not Significant
Able to boost my cognition	3.78	3.73	1.029	0.989	0.229	0.633	Not Significant
Able to reduce stress	3.80	4.01	1.045	1.067	0.589	0.444	Not Significant

Table 2.1 indicates that there is a significance difference between the Male & female students in negative thoughts, communication, cultural behavior, intellectual capacity and mental strength.

Table 2.2: ‘t’ test has been applied to find out significant difference between type of School and development factors

Variables	Mean		Standard Deviation		T value	P Value	Inference
	Government	Private	Government	Private			
Internet access helped me to develop my personal ability	4.19	4.14	0.731	0.720	0.459	0.499	Not Significant
Internet access developed my academic & personal performance	3.85	4.09	0.901	0.874	0.642	0.424	Not Significant
By using internet – I am able to overcome negative thoughts	3.17	3.71	1.080	0.998	0.407	0.524	Not Significant
Internet helps to develop my positive attitudes	3.83	3.82	1.098	1.057	0.855	0.356	Not Significant
I can develop my personality through usage of internet platform	4.04	3.95	0.993	0.917	5.702	0.018	Significant
I am able to develop my communication through usage of internet platform	4.26	4.32	0.807	0.829	0.561	0.454	Not Significant
Feeling relief by developing emotional thinking through internet platform	3.70	3.68	0.905	1.200	14.312	0.000	Significant
Able to enhance my mental strength	3.74	3.73	0.958	1.080	1.076	0.300	Not Significant
Able to develop my efficiency	3.96	4.05	0.803	0.768	3.443	0.064	Not Significant
Able to maintain my values in the society	3.98	3.61	0.882	1.033	11.664	0.001	Significant
Able to maintain my culture in the society	3.47	3.73	1.096	0.899	8.200	0.004	Significant
It helps to develop my confidence level	4.11	4.04	0.746	1.020	12.611	0.000	Significant
Able to develop adaptiveness in all situations.	4.00	3.82	0.974	1.057	0.344	0.558	Not Significant
Able to maintain my entertainment upto required level	4.09	4.13	1.072	1.122	0.508	0.477	Not Significant
It helps to enhance my intellectual capacity	4.04	3.84	0.826	0.885	0.499	0.480	Not Significant
Helps to develop my physical health	3.25	3.18	1.029	1.185	2.668	0.103	Not Significant
Helps to develop my mental health	3.49	3.57	1.043	1.151	0.255	0.614	Not Significant
Able to develop my sympathy level.	3.26	3.36	1.139	1.205	1.006	0.317	Not Significant
Able to boost my cognition	3.65	3.84	0.941	1.052	1.942	0.164	Not Significant
Able to reduce stress	3.83	4.04	1.080	1.038	0.322	0.571	Not Significant

Table 2.2 indicates that there is a significance difference between the government & private school in the development of personality, emotional thinking, own value creation, culture and confidence level.

Table 2.3: ‘t’ test has been applied to find out significant difference between Class (XI & XII) and development factors

Variables	Mean		Standard Deviation		T value	P Value	Inference
	XI	XII	XI	XII			
Internet access helped meto develop my personal ability	4.12	4.18	0.716	0.728	0.640	0.424	Not Significant
Internet access developed my academic & personal performance	4.20	3.90	0.753	0.923	2.973	0.086	Not Significant
By using internet – I am able to overcome negativethoughts	3.60	3.40	1.103	1.061	0.432	0.512	Not Significant
Internet helps to developmy positive attitudes	4.00	3.77	1.065	1.075	4.323	0.038	Significant
I can develop my personality through usageof internet platform	3.92	4.01	1.100	0.908	6.609	0.011	Significant
I am able to develop mycommunication through usage of internet platform	4.28	4.30	0.727	0.844	0.313	0.576	Not Significant
Feeling relief by developing emotional thinking through internet platform	3.76	3.67	1.149	1.041	0.201	0.654	Not Significant
Able to enhance mymental strength	3.80	3.71	1.027	1.021	0.108	0.743	Not Significant
Able to develop my efficiency	4.00	4.01	0.805	0.781	0.065	0.799	Not Significant
Able to maintain my values in the society	3.40	3.90	1.027	0.936	1.846	0.175	Not Significant
Able to maintain my culturein the society	3.48	3.64	1.178	0.949	6.389	0.12	Not Significant
It helps to develop myconfidence level	4.12	4.06	0.958	0.879	0.176	0.675	Not Significant
Able to develop adaptiveness in allsituations.	3.92	3.90	1.205	0.961	1.194	0.275	Not Significant
Able to maintain myentertainment up to required level	4.12	4.11	1.039	1.115	0.323	0.570	Not Significant
It helps to enhance myintellectual capacity	3.84	3.96	0.839	0.867	0.226	0.635	Not Significant
Helps to develop myphysical health	3.36	3.17	1.301	1.047	8.213	0.004	Significant
Helps to develop mymental health	3.36	3.58	1.420	0.980	23.883	0.000	Significant
Able to develop mysympathy level.	3.24	3.33	1.432	1.086	15.770	0.000	Significant
Able to boost my cognition	3.36	3.87	1.270	0.877	21.587	0.000	Significant
Able to reduce stress	3.76	3.99	1.314	0.972	12.609	0.000	Significant

Table 2.3 indicates that there is a significance difference between the XI & XII grade students in the development of positive attitudes, personality, physical health, mental health, sympathy, cognition level, reduction of stress.

Table 2.4: ‘F’ test has been applied to find out significant difference between parent’s education and development factors

Variables	Mean			Standard Deviation			T value	P Value	Inference
	Illiteracy	School Education	Higher education	Illiteracy	School Education	Higher education			
Internet access helped me to develop my personal ability	4.40	4.10	4.19	0.507	0.686	0.761	1.523	0.220	Not Significant
Internet access developed my academic & personal performance	4.20	4.12	3.85	0.414	0.627	1.048	3.853	0.022	Significant
By using internet – I am able to overcome negative thoughts	2.80	3.64	3.37	1.014	0.950	1.128	5.442	0.005	Significant
Internet helps to develop my positive attitudes	4.20	4.05	3.65	0.414	0.928	1.168	6.418	0.002	Significant
I can develop my personality through usage of internet platform	4.60	4.17	3.82	0.507	0.756	1.058	8.453	0.000	Significant
I am able to develop my communication through usage of internet platform	4.00	4.29	4.32	0.000	0.828	0.840	1.091	0.337	Not Significant
Feeling relief by developing emotional thinking through internet platform	3.40	3.88	3.58	0.507	0.935	1.161	3.614	0.028	Significant
Able to enhance my mental strength	3.40	3.81	3.71	1.242	0.797	1.130	1.202	0.302	Not Significant
Able to develop my efficiency	4.60	3.95	4.00	0.507	0.725	0.825	4.693	0.010	Significant
Able to maintain my values in the society	4.00	3.88	3.71	0.000	0.960	1.025	1.520	0.220	Not Significant
Able to maintain my culture in the society	3.80	3.93	3.37	0.775	0.860	1.054	12.673	0.000	Significant
It helps to develop my confidence level	4.20	4.29	3.92	0.414	0.703	1.008	6.646	0.001	Significant
Able to develop adaptiveness in all situations.	4.40	4.00	3.81	0.507	0.955	1.078	3.222	0.041	Significant
Able to maintain my entertainment upto required	4.20	4.17	4.06	0.414	0.654	1.346	0.377	0.686	Not Significant

Variables	Mean			Standard Deviation			T value	P Value	Inference
	Illiteracy	School Education	Higher education	Illiteracy	School Education	Higher education			
level									
It helps to enhance my intellectual capacity	3.80	4.00	3.90	0.775	0.657	0.982	0.669	0.513	Not Significant
Helps to develop my physical health	3.80	3.31	3.10	0.414	0.774	1.307	3.644	0.027	Significant
Helps to develop my mental health	3.80	3.67	3.42	1.207	0.780	1.255	2.391	0.093	Not Significant
Able to develop my sympathy level.	3.20	3.55	3.16	1.207	0.960	1.276	4.231	0.015	Significant
Able to boost my cognition	3.20	3.79	3.77	0.775	0.806	1.125	2.395	0.093	Not Significant
Able to reduce stress	3.60	3.90	3.98	0.507	0.871	1.201	0.994	0.371	Not Significant

Table 2.4 indicates that there is a significance difference between the parents' education in the development of academic & personal performance, negative thoughts, positive attitudes, personality, emotional thinking, efficiency, culture, confidence level, situation adaptiveness, physical health, sympathy.

Table 2.4: 'F' test has been applied to find out significant difference between parent's occupation and development factors

Variables	Mean				Standard Deviation				T value	P Value	Inference
	Government employee	Private Employee	Business	Others	Government employee	Private Employee	Business	Others			
D1	3.86	4.29	4.20	4.00	0.647	0.771	0.697	0.583	5.227	0.002	Significant
D2	3.93	3.90	4.16	3.94	0.601	0.949	1.091	0.529	1.463	0.225	Not Significant
D3	3.64	3.40	3.64	3.17	0.727	1.152	1.098	0.966	2.629	0.050	Significant
D4	4.14	3.75	3.52	4.22	0.647	1.162	1.212	0.634	6.228	0.000	Significant
D5	3.57	4.00	4.00	4.28	0.831	1.022	0.944	0.738	4.476	0.004	Significant
D6	3.93	4.38	4.52	4.00	0.894	0.714	0.760	0.952	8.184	0.000	Significant
D7	3.93	3.62	3.44	4.06	0.601	1.025	1.454	0.627	4.598	0.004	Significant
D8	3.71	3.88	3.60	3.50	0.596	0.872	1.452	0.906	2.549	0.056	Not Significant
D9	3.93	3.98	4.04	4.11	0.463	0.869	0.877	0.572	0.555	0.645	Not Significant
D10	3.93	3.85	3.36	4.11	0.712	0.910	1.237	0.744	7.653	0.000	Significant
D11	3.93	3.46	3.52	3.89	0.601	1.050	1.070	0.945	4.238	0.006	Significant
D12	4.21	4.10	3.80	4.28	0.682	0.793	1.241	0.656	3.728	0.012	Significant
D13	4.14	3.94	3.48	4.22	0.647	1.030	1.277	0.538	7.311	0.000	Significant
D14	4.50	4.08	3.96	4.11	0.741	1.161	1.350	0.572	2.313	0.076	Not Significant
D15	4.00	3.90	3.80	4.17	0.541	0.928	0.986	0.607	2.086	0.102	Not Significant
D16	3.00	3.27	3.16	3.28	0.765	1.215	1.295	0.656	0.764	0.515	Not Significant
D17	3.36	3.65	3.36	3.56	0.906	1.093	1.332	0.839	1.625	0.183	Not Significant
D18	3.71	3.27	3.12	3.39	0.891	1.199	1.404	0.834	2.499	0.060	Not Significant
D19	4.07	3.65	3.80	3.72	0.712	1.048	1.174	0.738	2.073	0.104	Not Significant
D20	4.21	3.96	3.88	3.72	0.951	1.130	1.185	0.656	1.804	0.146	Not Significant

Table 2.5 indicates that there is a significance difference between the parents' occupation in the development of personal ability, overcoming negative thoughts, positive attitudes, personality, communication, emotional thinking, values, culture, confidence level, situation adaptiveness.

MAJOR FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

The study has broadly four objectives, since it is an exploratory study in detailed analysis of which has revealed major findings. This chapter highlights the major findings of the study.

Profile of the Respondents

The study includes the following personal profiles of the students. Gender, Type of school, Class or Standard or Grade, Parents education, Parents occupation. The analysis in respect of the personal profiles reveals the following findings:

Majority of the students are female from private school studying in grade XII and their parents are working in private companies with higher education qualification.

The analysis in respect of the development factors reveals the following findings:

- Personal profile - **Gender** indicates that there is a significance difference between the Male & female students in negative thoughts, communication, cultural behavior, intellectual capacity and mental strength in their personal development factors.
- Personal profile – **Type of School** indicates that there is a significance difference between the government & private school in the development of personality, emotional thinking, own value creation, culture and confidence level in their personal development factors.
- Personal profile – **Class (XI & XII)** indicates that there is a significance difference between the XI & XII grade students in the development of positive attitudes, personality, physical health, mental health, sympathy, cognition level, reduction of stress in their personal development factors.
- Personal profile – **Parent's education** indicates that there is a significance difference between the parents' education in the development of academic & personal performance, negative thoughts, positive attitudes, personality, emotional thinking, efficiency, culture, confidence level, situation adaptiveness, physical health, sympathy in their personal development factors.
- Personal profile – **Parent's occupation** indicates that there is a significance difference between the parents' occupation in the development of personal ability, overcoming negative thoughts, positive attitudes, personality, communication, emotional thinking, values, culture, confidence level, and situation adaptiveness in their personal development factors.

CONCLUSION

Internet access helps us to improve our quality of life. The internet is generally defined as a global networking system which was used in different production and service sector. Internet access exerts a huge impact on human life. With the internet access life has become more convenient for the individuals, which is very useful in day-to-day activities in different areas like E-banking, E-ticketing, and E-commerce etc.

In addition, students have the opportunity to enjoy the benefits of internet access in their personal and academic uses. In the present scenario, Students are personally involved with internet access at every stage of the life. The benefits of internet access for the students in academic & personal uses are many.

If students use internet smartly, they can develop them with good personality, positive thinking, confidence, good communication, intellectual capacity, good physical and mental health by accessing E-new papers & journals, E-books, business or science resources, higher education information, research etc. - which will be useful for their career and academic aspects, if they use diversely the student can develop only good entertainment time.

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